

Vibration Characteristics of Laminated Composite Plates

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ABSTRACT

Vibration characteristics of laminated carbon-epoxy composite plates are investigated experimentally and analytically in this paper. The plates considered are rectangular and clamped at four edges. They are composed of symmetrically laminated eight layers.

Vibration experiments are conducted by using a holographic apparatus. Plates are sinusoidally excited by a small piezo-electric exciter, and their resonances are detected by observing sharp sound change emitted from the plates during tuning. Holograms of natural vibration modes are obtained by a time-average method. Analytical vibration characteristics are obtained by utilizing Galerkin's method and compared with the experimental results. Fair agreements on natural vibration frequencies and modes are obtained. The experimental and analytical natural modes of off-axis plates are found to be quite different from the ones of the orthotropic plates whose principal material axes coincide with the plate reference coordinates. This phenomenon is due to the fact that coupling terms between bending and twisting are not zero for the off-axis plates.

INTRODUCTION

Vibration characteristics of laminated composite plates are much different from the ones of isotropic plates. Several theoretical papers [1,2,3,4] have been published on the natural vibration frequencies and modes of the laminated composite plates. But comparisons with experimental results have not been done except by Thornton and Clary [4]. Therefore, more correlation studies are considered to be necessary. In this paper natural vibration frequencies and modes of laminated carbon-epoxy rectangular plates clamped at all edges are investigated experimentally and theoretically. A holographic apparatus is used to get the natural vibration modes.

COMPOSITE PLATES AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

All plates are symmetrically laminated with eight carbon-epoxy layers. Twelve different laminate configurations are selected for investigation. Five of them are the unidirectional laminates whose fiber orientations are aligned in 0° , 30° , 45° , 60° and 90° with respect to the plate reference axis. Five of them are symmetrical angle-ply plates whose fiber directions are $\pm 15^\circ$, $\pm 30^\circ$, $\pm 45^\circ$, $\pm 60^\circ$ and $\pm 75^\circ$. The

other two are symmetrical cross-ply plates and $[+22.5^\circ / -47.5^\circ]$ plates. The thickness of each layer is 0.125 mm. Three kinds of plate dimensions are used. They are 200 mm x 200 mm, 300 mm x 200 mm, 400 mm x 200 mm. The plates are clamped at all edges.

The plates are excited by a small piezo-electric exciter which is connected to an oscillator. Natural vibration frequencies are identified by a sharp sound change emitted from the plates during tuning. Holographic interferograms of natural vibration modes are obtained by a time average method [5]. The holographic apparatus used in this experiment is shown in Fig.1. Argon laser is used in this apparatus. Interference fringes in the holographic interferograms represent equal contour lines of vibration modes.

Fig. 1. Experimental apparatus.

CALCULATION OF NATURAL VIBRATION FREQUENCIES AND MODES

The vibrational differential equation of symmetrical laminated plates is given by Eq.(1).

$$D_{11}w_{,xxxx} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})w_{,xxyy} + D_{22}w_{,yyyy} + 4D_{16}w_{,xxxY} + 4D_{26}w_{,xYY} = \rho h \omega^2 w \quad (1)$$

where h , ρ , D_{ij} , w and ω are the total thickness, the mass density, the bending stiffness, the deflection and the circular frequency of the plates respectively. The bending stiffnesses D_{16} and D_{26} [6] are not zero when the fiber directions are not aligned with the plate reference axis shown in Fig.2. The boundary conditions of clamped plates are given by

$$w = w_{,x} = 0 \quad \text{at } x = 0, a \quad (2)$$

$$w = w_{,y} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = 0, b \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2. Composite plates.

The following vibration mode is chosen to get the solution.

$$w(x,y) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N A_{mn} \left[\cos \frac{(m-1)\pi x}{a} - \cos \frac{(m+1)\pi x}{a} \right] x \left[\cos \frac{(n-1)\pi y}{b} - \cos \frac{(n+1)\pi y}{b} \right] \quad (4)$$

The assumed deflection function satisfies the boundary conditions given by Eqs.(2) and (3). Application of Galerkin's method to Eq.(1) with the above assumed function gives the characteristic equation which gives the natural vibration frequencies.

COMPARISON OF NATURAL VIBRATION FREQUENCIES AND MODES

Following material properties obtained experimentally are used for the numerical calculations.

$$\begin{aligned} E_L &= 11,200 \text{ kgf/mm}^2, E_T = 920 \text{ kgf/mm}^2, G_{LT} = 500 \text{ kgf/mm}^2 \\ \nu_{LT} &= 0.35, \rho = 1.60 \times 10^{-6} / \text{g kgf sec}^2 / \text{mm}^4 \end{aligned}$$

where g is the acceleration of gravity. The natural vibration frequencies are calculated by taking $m = 1.9$ and $n = 1.9$ in Eq.(4). The experimental natural vibration frequencies are shown in Tables 1, 2 and 3 with the analytical values. Tables 1, 2 and 3 are for the case of $a/b=1, 1.5$ and 2 respectively. The results are also shown graphically in Figs. 3, 4 and 5. In Figs. 3-5 the analytical results for the case of orthotropic plates ($D_{16}=D_{26}=0$) are also shown. There is little difference between the natural vibration frequencies of the eight layered angle-ply plates and the orthotropic plates. But the difference between the off-axis plates and the orthotropic plates is rather large. This difference is due to the bending and twisting coupling terms (D_{16} and D_{26}) of the unidirectional off-axis plates.

Experimental and analytical vibration modes are shown in Figs. 6, 7, 8 and 9. Fig. 6 gives the experimental and analytical natural vibration modes of a $+30^\circ$ off-axis plate whose aspect ratio is equal to 1. Fig. 7 is for the case of a $+30^\circ$ angle-ply plate whose outermost fiber direction is $+30^\circ$ with respect to the x-axis. Figs. 7 and 8 are for the case of a $+30^\circ$ off-axis and a $+30^\circ$ angle-ply plate with $a/b = 1.5$ respectively. The calculated vibration amplitudes are normalized by taking $\sum \Delta \epsilon = 1$. Four or five equal contour lines in each calculated mode correspond to $w = 0, +0.1, +1, +2$ and $+3$ respectively. The first fringes of the experimental modes correspond to the equal contour line of the displacement $9.85 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m}$. From these figures it can be said that the experimental vibration modes agree well with the analytical vibration modes. The oblique nodal lines observed in these figures are due to the coupling effect between bending and twisting.

CONCLUSIONS

The natural vibration frequencies and modes of carbon-epoxy laminated plates are investigated experimentally and analytically. The experiments are carried out by using holographic apparatus. The experimental results agree fairly well with the analytical results. The laminated plates with large coupling terms between bending and twisting have the vibration modes quite different from the ones of the orthotropic plates whose principal material axis coincide with the plate reference axis.

REFERENCES

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Table 1 Natural Frequencies of Plates with a/b = 1.0 (in Hz)

θ	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	f_5
0°	189/230	260/294	397/427	525/604	566/623
30°	174/204	281/313	420/424	439/501	566/630
45°	171/196	304/332	424/453	445/489	618/675
60°	186/204	286/313	429/424	457/501	580/630
90°	216/230	278/294	395/427	552/604	570/628
$\pm 15^\circ$	202/227	286/314	431/468	518/582	606/663
$\pm 30^\circ$	184/223	329/368	438/524	527/584	605/691
$\pm 45^\circ$	187/221	371/425	433/464	580/677	687/770
$\pm 60^\circ$	204/223	344/368	476/524	530/584	636/691
$\pm 75^\circ$	198/227	279/314	420/468	521/582	596/663
$[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_{\text{sym}}$	188/230	340/417	467/537	575/650	634/744
$[\pm 22.5^\circ/\mp 67.5^\circ]_{\text{sym}}$	198/227	339/376	472/537	553/618	609/684

Values are given as experimental/theoretical.

Table 2 Natural Frequencies of Plates with a/b = 1.5 (in Hz)

θ	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	f_5
0°	110/119	217/207	238/279	325/343	363/362
30°	122/127	210/220	277/290	308/326	413/441
45°	143/147	217/214	305/310	362/365	424/432
60°	171/179	223/218	283/290	381/389	459/475
90°	215/219	243/238	287/281	350/355	455/459
$\pm 15^\circ$	108/124	205/226	250/278	335/366	367/397
$\pm 30^\circ$	147/138	280/265	309/293	407/421	475/475
$\pm 45^\circ$	152/162	236/260	357/385	370/404	473/505
$\pm 60^\circ$	- /189	- /251	- /347	- /479	- /489
$\pm 75^\circ$	206/211	231/242	280/300	357/388	462/506
$[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_{\text{sym}}$	149/157	242/267	357/375	415/445	427/466
$[\pm 22.5^\circ/\mp 67.5^\circ]_{\text{sym}}$	133/142	247/274	293/304	400/432	429/479

Values are given as experimental/theoretical.

Table 3 Natural Frequencies of Plates with a/b = 2.0 (in Hz)

θ	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	f_5
0°	92/86	157/169	200/186	250/249	277/307
30°	109/105	160/159	223/235	246/254	305/325
45°	122/134	154/168	205/224	276/296	322/354
60°	167/173	189/191	225/226	267/279	334/350
90°	- /216	- /225	- /243	- /276	- /325
$\pm 15^\circ$	93/92	172/173	219/208	280/273	300/306
$\pm 30^\circ$	122/112	193/184	276/262	299/291	357/347
$\pm 45^\circ$	128/143	176/199	252/281	340/363	351/391
$\pm 60^\circ$	184/179	225/212	271/265	347/338	429/429
$\pm 75^\circ$	201/206	221/221	247/250	287/294	341/355
$[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_{\text{sym}}$	135/141	175/188	270/280	361/366	378/395
$[\pm 22.5^\circ/\mp 67.5^\circ]_{\text{sym}}$	112/117	172/186	265/282	273/298	334/350

Values are given as experimental/theoretical.

Fig. 3. Comparison of experimental and analytical natural frequencies of plates with $a/b = 1.0$.

Fig. 4. Comparison of experimental and analytical natural frequencies of plates with $a/b = 1.5$.

Fig. 5. Comparison of experimental and analytical natural frequencies of plates with $a/b = 2.0$.

Fig. 6. First five vibration modes.
 (30° off-axis, $a/b=1.0$)

Fig. 7. First five vibration modes.
 ($+30^\circ$ angle-ply, $a/b=1.0$)

122 Hz

127 Hz

210 Hz

220 Hz

277 Hz

290 Hz

308 Hz

326 Hz

413 Hz

441 Hz

Fig. 8. First five vibration modes. (30° off-axis, $a/b=1.5$)

147 Hz

138 Hz

280 Hz

265 Hz

309 Hz

293 Hz

407 Hz

421 Hz

475 Hz

475 Hz

Fig. 9. First five vibration modes. ($\pm 30^\circ$ angle-ply, $a/b=1.5$)